

Five Representative Publications

- P1: “[Assessing Nonadiabatic Dynamics Methods in Long Timescales](#)”, S. Mukherjee, Y. Lassmann, R. S. Mattos, B. Demoulin, B. F. E. Curchod, M. Barbatti, *J. Chem. Theory Comp.* **21**, 29 (2025).
- P2: “[A Hessian free method to prevent zero-point energy leakage in classical trajectories](#)”, S. Mukherjee, M. Barbatti, *J. Chem. Theory Comp.* **18**, 4109 (2022).
- P3: “[Simulations of molecular photodynamics in long timescales](#)”, S. Mukherjee, M. Pinheiro Jr., B. Demoulin, M. Barbatti, *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. A* **380**, 20200382 (2022).
- P4: “[Intersystem crossing and internal conversion dynamics with GAIMS-TeraChem: Excited states relaxation in 2-cyclopentenone](#)”, S. Mukherjee, S. Varganov, *J. Chem. Phys.* **155**, 174107 (2021).
- P5: “[Beyond Born-Oppenheimer theory for ab initio constructed diabatic potential energy surfaces of singlet H₃⁺ to study reaction dynamics using coupled 3D time-dependent wave-packet approach](#)”, S. Ghosh, S. Mukherjee, S. Mandal, B. Mukherjee, R. Sharma, P. Chaudhury, S. Adhikari, *J. Chem. Phys.* **147**, 074105 (2017) [Joint First Author].

Ten Recent Publications

- RP1: “[Surface Hopping with Fully Correlated Methods](#)”, E. G. F. de Miranda, R. S. Mattos, S. Mukherjee, J. M. Toldo, C. Ho Choi, M. T. do N. Varella, M. Barbatti, *J. Chem. Theory Comp.* **22**, 1 (2026).
- RP2: “[Ehrenfest dynamics with spontaneous localization](#)”, A. A. Tomaz, R. S. Mattos, S. Mukherjee, M. Barbatti, *J. Chem. Phys.* **163**, 214114 (2025).
- RP3: “[Legion: A Platform for Gaussian Wavepacket Nonadiabatic Dynamics](#)”, R. S. Mattos, S. Mukherjee, M. Barbatti, *J. Chem. Theory Comp.* **21**, 2189 (2025).
- RP4: “[Assessing Nonadiabatic Dynamics Methods in Long Timescales](#)”, S. Mukherjee, Y. Lassmann, R. S. Mattos, B. Demoulin, B. F. E. Curchod, M. Barbatti, *J. Chem. Theory Comp.* **21**, 29 (2025).
- RP5: “[Quantum Dynamics from Classical Trajectories](#)”, R. S. Mattos, S. Mukherjee, R. S. Mattos, M. Barbatti, *J. Chem. Theory Comp.* **20**, 7728 (2024).
- RP6: “[Prediction Challenge: Simulating Rydberg Photoexcited Cyclobutanone with Surface Hopping Dynamics based on Different Electronic Structure Methods](#)”, S. Mukherjee, R. S. Mattos, J. M. Toldo, H. Lischka, M. Barbatti, *J. Chem. Phys.* **160**, 154306 (2024).
- RP7: “[Recommendations for velocity adjustments in surface hopping](#)”, J. M. Toldo, R. S. Mattos, M. Pinheiro, S. Mukherjee, M. Barbatti, *J. Chem. Theory Comp.* **20**, 614 (2024).
- RP8: “[Non-Kasha fluorescence of pyrene emerges from a dynamic equilibrium between excited states](#)”, G. Braun, I. Borges Jr., A. Aquino, H. Lischka, F. Plasser, S. A. do Monte, E. Ventura, S. Mukherjee, M. Barbatti, *J. Chem. Phys.* **157**, 154305 (2022).
- RP9: “[A Hessian free method to prevent zero-point energy leakage in classical trajectories](#)”, S. Mukherjee, M. Barbatti, *J. Chem. Theory Comp.* **18**, 4109 (2022).
- RP10: “[Pre-Dewar bond modulates protonated azaindole photodynamics](#)”, R. Mansour, S. Mukherjee, M. Pinheiro Jr., J. Noble, C. Jouvét, M. Barbatti, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **24**, 12346 (2022).